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[Photo Captioning]

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1. Introduction

1.1 Short Description

Photo captioning automatically generates a natural language description of an image which connects two fields of machine language that is computer vision for image recognition and natural language processing. This app uses artificial intelligence (AI) which are programmed to think like human for object detection. This is an android app where people upload photo which is detected through AI and suggests related captions. (TechTarget, 2020).

Computer vision is the field of artificial intelligence that enables computer to see, identify, process image and provide appropriate output as human vision does (techopedia, 2019). For example, as shown in Figure 1: Example of computer vision, it is used in self-driving car which uses ultrasonic sensors, multiple cameras, lidar, radar to detect objects, traffic signals to drive safely (Marr, 2019).

Figure 1: Example of computer vision (Mihajlovic, 2019)

Natural language processing (NLP) refers to artificial intelligence (AI) method that helps computer understand, interpret and manipulate human language. It is required when you want your system to perform as your instructions. The input and output of natural language

processing can be either speech or written speech (tutorialspoint, 2020). Example: Email filters, language translation, search results (TABLEAU SOFTWARE, 2020).

1.2 Problem Domain

Taking picture has never been easier and adding few texts to it adds enormously to their value to other people. People make their own conclusion of photo without caption.

Some of the major problems are:

- Many people struggle while writing captions in social media platforms. It is significant to a lot of campaigns and advertisements.
- When people share photos on social media, the photo might include graphic violence or it might not be appropriate for people under the age of 18 or certain age group.
- Visually impaired person relies on sound to describe a scene.

1.3 Photo captioning as solution

In today's world, photo captioning is highly demanded technology. Caption convey information of four W's in journalism that is who, what, where and when. Captions with interesting photographs can glint reader's interest Photo captioning is especially designed to save people's time. Some of the major use of photo captioning app are as follows:

- Photo captioning plays major role in social media platforms. Captions are important component as it communicates the background story of photos and increase the engagement with audience. Photo captioning suggests captions to the photos.
- As this app gives the description of the photo, nature sensitive content can be separated. Message can be sent before viewing photos. Those kind of photos or user can be blocked later.

Figure 2: Instagram sensitive content message

Instagram send message to all users before viewing sensitive content.

Figure 3: Facebook blocked image

If you upload or send Figure 3: Facebook blocked image , this image in message through facebook then it temporarily blocks your account for three days. The background of this image involves sexually explicit behaviour of children under the age of 18.

- The description generated by captioning app can be converted into voice through text to speech which can help visually impaired people.

2. Literature review

2.1 Potential end users

A questionnaire survey was conducted via google forms to figure out the clients or potential end users of the Photo captioning. It was found that 60% of people having 15-30 age group mostly use the photo captioning apps or software. From the survey, the targeted users or potential users of photo captioning apps are students, researchers, celebrities and developers. In average, people concluded that photo captioning is only 50% accurate and they mostly use it for social media. 75% of the total people use photo captioning apps or software in their mobile device whereas rest uses Laptop/PC.

2.2 Review on similar system

2.2.1 Facebook

Facebook uses artificial intelligence to automatically generate captions for photos in news feeds for visually impaired people and the tool is called Automatic Alternative Text which joins with text to speech engines. Facebook follows the open-sourcing of image processing library spectrum and natural language processing framework PyText. Facebook uses modular plug-and-play framework called Pythia which answers questions related to visual data and automatically generates image captions (WIGGERS, 2019).

Figure 4: Facebook generating captions

2.2.2 Google

Image captioning software in google is part of TensorFlow machine learning kit. Google has released 'Show and Tell', a free software algorithm capable of automatically captioning images with up to 93.9 percent accuracy. Google's new system is faster and better at identifying objects and made its image captioning system as open source (Dudau , 2016).

Figure 5: Google captioning image (Walker, 2016)

2.2.3 Aipoly Vision

Aipoly Vision is a color and object recognition app that helps visually impaired and color-blind people to understand their surroundings. There is no need of taking picture as the app constantly sees and thinks, is able to identify three objects in a second. It uses convolutional neural networks, an innovative architecture of algorithms which is inspired by the animal visual cortex (Fixes, 2016).

Figure 6: Aipoly Vision detecting image (Cabrera, 2016)

2.3 Literature Review Analysis

Through my comparison with the similar systems and my system, I found many difference in features between my system and others. The basic feature of my system is to take input via image and suggest captions accordingly.

Features	Facebook	Google	Aipoly Vision
Login/Register	Yes	Yes	No
Payment	No	No	Yes
Online	Yes	Yes	No
Image captioning	Yes	Yes	No
Accurate	Yes	Yes	Yes
Text to speech	Yes	Yes	Yes

2.4 Algorithm

Convolution Neural Network (CNN) and Long short-term memory (LSTM) which is artificial recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture is used for captioning image. Image captioning is divided into two modules that is image-based module which extracts the feature of the image and language-based module which translates the features given by image-based model into a natural sentence. Convolution Neural Network model is used for image-based model and Long short-term memory model is used for language-based model (Pardeshi, 2019). CNN takes an input image, process it and classify it under certain categories. LSTM was created as the solution to short-term memory (Prabhu, 2018).

3. Development

3.1 Methodology

I. Waterfall model:

Waterfall model is simple to understand, follow and arrange task. In waterfall model each phase must be completed before the next phase can begin with no overlap between the phases. As our project is short and the requirement is well known, clear and fixed, this model can be considered as one of the development approaches for my project. This would be seamless to use for newer developers (TechTarget, 2020).

II. Spiral model:

Spiral model is flexible model which enables the development team to build a highly customized product. Spiral model uses the approach of Prototyping Model which builds a prototype at the start of each phase as risk handling technique. This model is able to accommodate new changes or functionality at a later stage of the development. Hence, it is also considered as one of the appropriate methodologies for my project (GeeksforGeeks, 2020).

III. Scrum:

Scrum falls under Agile Development Methodology. In scrum changes can be supported and integrated into a project in progress. In scrum tasks are prioritized by order of importance, the task to be completed first will probably affect return on investment the most. Hence, this methodology can also be considered appropriate for my project (Agilest, 2020).

3.2 Methodology selected/rejected

I. Waterfall model:

This model is rejected because it is inflexible for the project. Waterfall model does not have back track mechanism so it is difficult to update or make changes in the system. Hence, this model makes it difficult to respond to any changes brought in the system.

II. Spiral model:

This model is rejected because it is highly customized to each project and is quite complex which requires skilled and experience project manager to determine how to apply it. The cycle continues without any clear termination condition which increases the risk of not meeting the budget and schedules.

III. Scrum:

The reason of using SCRUM methodology is that it meets each and every criteria of the app development process. The idea of developing an application sprint by sprint while conducting daily meetings and discussion with the supervisor and reader sounds very fruitful and can provide the best result in return. SCRUM guarantees time management, increase in adaptability, step control and promoting team work among the group members which are the perfect reasons why SCRUM methodology is being used in the fitness application (Chron, 2020).

3.3 Selected Methodology

While choosing development methodology, I chose SCRUM under Agile Methodology. Other development methodologies were not as efficient as SCRUM.

Figure 7: SCRUM (Medlock, 2017)

SCRUM methodology work flow is shown below in respect to our application:

- Product Backlog:**

Product backlog is created first where prioritized features of the Fitness app is kept as user stories. The user stories are kept in “As a I need So that” format which helps to estimate the size of the task. The backlog evolves and changes every sprint when new fitness features are added. The features of the app include exercise tutorials, reminders, progress tracking etc.
- Sprint Planning:**

Sprint Planning is done after the end of every sprint of the fitness app. Our group performs a small meet up to discuss about the user stories of the fitness app in each sprint and also discuss about what should we focus more on the next sprint.

- **Sprint Backlog:**
Sprint Backlog consists the list of all the prioritized user stories. The group has a solid understanding of all the user stories available in the sprint backlog which is the outcome of the previous sprint planning and meetings among the group members.
- **Sprint:**
Sprint is a time box for work completion. Here, the group members are assigned with a work according to the sprint backlog. It is a time period of 1-3 weeks or may sometimes even take a month. During the sprint, Daily scrum occurs between group members. It is a stand-up meeting where group members explain what they have completed, what they are currently working on and what part of the work they are unable to accomplish.
- **Shippable Product:**
Shippable product is the outcome of the sprint conducted. The group decides whether the product is ready to ship or some additional features should be added to the application before shipping.
- **Sprint Review and Retrospective:**
Sprint Review is done between the group members where each member shows what contribution they have made on the fitness app and discuss among each other. Sprint Retrospective is carried out by the group members where the group brainstorms what more can they do to improve their process in the fitness app.
- **Burn Down Chart:**
Burn down Chart shows the progress of completion of the task in each sprint of our application. When the point hits zero, it denotes the successful completion of a task in a sprint (Gurendo , 2015).

The above workflow delivers a single sprint. The looping process never ends until the deployment of the final potentially shippable product. This workflow has helped to improve the time management of our application. The methodology strives to make a complete application according to user requirements with their feedback.

3.4 Tools and technique

3.4.1 Tools

Tools	Why required?
High specification laptop	High Specs Laptop with i7 8th gen processor, powerful Graphics Card and 8GB or more RAM is required for smooth development of the application which includes designing, coding and testing.
MySQL	MySQL database is required to store the system's data locally. It provides great interface for storing and retrieving data.
Programming Languages	Programming Languages Python is to be used for developing the app as they are the most popular and understandable language among other programming languages.
PyCharm IDE	PyCharm IDE is required for coding purpose. Using PyCharm for coding python is beneficial.
Microsoft Office	Microsoft Office is without doubt the best software for formatting reports, saving reports and managing context in relation with the application.

3.4.2 Techniques

Techniques	Why is it used?
Case study	Researching into a similar system over a period of time to study the overall app.
Literature review analysis	Critical analysis of Photo captioning software to find out what features to add and what not to.
Algorithms	Basic algorithms required for the application are to be used for properly initiation of the functions.
Brainstorming	Thinking on our own to find out what possible features to add, how to make it user friendly and how to increase its accuracy.
Simplicity	Simple application with powerful and effective features is more preferred than fancy application with useless features.

4. Project Plan

4.1 Work breakdown structure

4.2 Gantt Chart

5. Probable issues

5.1 Risk factors

- Hardware crash
- Poor time estimation
- Supervisor on temporary or permanent leave
- Below par computing specs
- Software Crash

5.2 Fallback plan for the risks

- Backup data on cloud storage services
- Proper planning and focus on important work first
- Take help from other teachers
- Use free cloud computing services like GCP.
- The software should be updated frequently to remove bugs and to stay updated with the version of android so that the software does not crash.

5.3 Social, legal and ethical issues

5.3.1 Social issues

- Unacceptance of the application
- Data misuse

5.3.2 Legal issues

- Application restricted by the government
- Interpretation of contract

5.3.3 Ethical issues

- Excessive Cost
- Interest Conflicts

5.4 Solution for social, legal and ethical issue raised

5.4.1 Solution for social issue

- After each sprint, acknowledgment testing should be done.
- Information should be stored with security within the storage.

5.4.2 Solution for legal issue

- Consultation with an experienced individual and utilization of lawful strengths if required.
- The words on the contract should be clear and brief.

5.4.3 Solution for ethical issue

- By reducing the amount of time spent on unnecessary tasks and allowing more people specifically clients to be involved in the project.
- Develop a plan to work on each conflict, the tools and services utilized should be in lined so that the application can be utilized.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Key findings of the proposal

Photo captioning is the application which suggests user description of the image. The system includes python language, computer vision for image detection and natural language processing. All the components of the system work together and provides appropriate result to the end user.

This report includes all the basic ideas, working mechanism, similar technology, AI technology, Algorithms, Programming language, Methodology, Tools and Resources Required. All of the things which requires to build the system is explained in the report. The report also consists of Work Break Down Structure for work classification and Gantt Chart for time management.

6.2 Recommendations

In order to make the application more effective, the system can be made larger by advertising and suggesting people to use this application as it is free for everyone. The research paper the wireframe and design of the web application can be modified and made better than represented in the 8. Appendix section.

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8. Appendix

8.1 Wireframe

The registration wireframe features the UCaption logo at the top. Below it are five input fields: FullName, Username, Email, Password, and Gender. A Register button is positioned below the fields. At the bottom, there is a link for users who already have an account.

UCaption

FullName

Username

Email

Password

Gender

Register

Already have an account? [Login](#)

Figure 8: Wireframe for Registration

The login wireframe features the UCaption logo at the top. Below it are two input fields: username and Password. A Login button is positioned below the fields. Below the button is a link for users who forgot their password.

UCaption

username

Password

Login

[Forgot your Password?](#)

Figure 9: Wireframe for Login

Figure 10: Wireframe for Homepage

Figure 11: Wireframe for scanning photo

Figure 12: Wireframe for generating caption